

An ecodesigned reagent-free paper-based electrochemical sensor modified with carbon black for the detection of essential oils

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ABSTRACT

In the era of sustainability, the use of natural compounds as antimicrobial compounds is the rational selection to avoid the release of pollutants into the environment. Among natural compounds, essential oils are characterized by reliable antimicrobial activity and their use is estimated to grow in the future, thus their detection is an asked point. Herein, we report an electrochemical reagent-free paper-based device for the detection of essential oils, namely thymol, eugenol, and carvacrol by adding 5 μL of solution onto the electrode. We functionalized the working electrode with carbon black by drop casting, demonstrating for the first time the improved sensitivity in essential oil detection using this affordable nanomaterial. To deliver a reagent-free device, the paper-based electrode was loaded with the working buffer for asking the end-user only the addition of the sample. This sensor detected the selected essential oils in a dynamic linear range of up to 16 ppm, with a detection limit equal to 0.1, 0.1, and 0.2 ppm for thymol, eugenol, and carvacrol, respectively. Moreover, the sensor's sustainability was evaluated using the RGBfast method, highlighting its whiteness compared to conventional chromatographic techniques. The reliable results obtained using the paper-based electrochemical sensor demonstrated the versatility, eco-friendliness, and practicality of this sensing tool, enlarging its use in essential oil detection.

1. Introduction

Essential oils (EOs) are mainly solutions composed of volatile organic molecules extracted using steam distillation from officinal plants. The extracted compounds' molecular structures and functional groups are various, spanning from alkene to phenol and ester, and a common molecular property is the terpene motif [1]. One of the most abundant families of these volatile molecules is the monoterpene, which is a compound with 10 carbons such as camphor, carvone, limonene, citral, citronellal, citronellol, geraniol, eucalyptol, linalool, menthol, and thymol, which differ from the main functional group [2]. Among all these molecules, the most useful components of the EOs are the phenolic compounds, which very often give the plant a characteristic odour. Phenols fraction is responsible for one of the most significant EO characteristics, namely antimicrobial property, which is associated with the interactions of natural phenols with cellular membranes, inducing a

variation in the double phospholipid layer properties [3]. Moreover, another important property of phenolic compounds is their antioxidant activity, protecting healthy cells from free oxygen radicals [4]. These features boosted the use of EOs in several fields. For instance, eugenol is used in aquaculture as fish anesthetic products (commercial formulations AQUI-S (20E) and AQUI-S(TM)) [5] and in dental applications, where serves as an analgesic and antibacterial agent in temporary dental cement and cavity dressings [6]. Furthermore, its antioxidant properties make it a valuable ingredient in food preservation, extending shelf life [7]. Carvacrol was reported to exhibit potent activity against biofilms formed by foodborne pathogens such as *Listeria monocytogenes*, making it an essential compound for improving food safety [8]. Additionally, its incorporation into edible films and coatings enhances the antimicrobial efficacy of packaging materials, ensuring better preservation of perishable products [9]. Its use in the vapor phase also demonstrated the ability to inactivate the airborne SARS-CoV-2 [10]. Thymol is adopted as

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a novel botanical pesticide against insects and bacteria [11]. Moreover, its use in personal care products such as mouthwashes enhances oral hygiene by reducing plaque and gingivitis [12].

Actually, only some countries regulate the concentration of EOs; for instance, Japan sets a maximum residue limit equal to 0.05 ppm according to the regulation of Food Sanitation Act No 233, 1947, established by the Ministry of Health, Labour, and Welfare (under MHLW Notification No. 375, 2021). However, safety levels are reported in the literature. Thymol can enhance the activity of conventional fungicides when used combined with e.g. tebuconazole at concentrations around 50 ppm, ensuring both safety and efficacy while minimizing environmental impact [13]. Carvacrol use in food packaging demonstrated a minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) ranging from 75 to 375 ppm toward different microorganisms, improving safety and sensory quality [14]. These regulatory and suggested concentration values depicted the need for sensitive detection methods.

Eugenol, carvacrol, and thymol have usually been detected using chromatography such as liquid chromatography combined with fluorimetric detection [15], ultra-performance liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry [16], gas chromatography coupled with triple quadrupole tandem mass spectrometry operated in electron ionization mode [17]. However, these methods, even if characterized by high sensitivity, selectivity, and accuracy, require expensive instrumentation, time-consuming analysis, and skilled personnel. In addition to these drawbacks, traditional chromatographic analytical methods face specific challenges related to green analysis. For example, liquid chromatography techniques require solvents such as acetonitrile and methanol, which are not environmentally friendly and generate considerable waste during analyses [15,16]. The drawbacks emphasize the need for sustainable analytical methods that minimize solvent consumption and waste generation while maintaining high analytical performance. Despite the many benefits of electrochemical sensors, such as the cost-effectiveness, rapid analysis, sensitivity, potential for miniaturization, and on-site measurement, the state of the art related to electrochemical sensors for detecting EOs is limited to a few examples. Robledo et al. developed a simple and rapid method based on the use of a glassy carbon electrode and linear sweep voltammetry to determine thymol and carvacrol in nonaqueous media, namely acetonitrile with tetrabutylammonium perchlorate. The intensity of the oxidation peak centred at about +1.3 V (vs Ag/AgCl) allowed the detection of the target analyte in the concentration range from 13 to 195 ppm and 12 to 180 ppm for thymol and carvacrol, respectively [18].

Moving toward the aqueous solution, Stankovic used boron-doped diamond electrode and square-wave voltammetry to quantify thymol in Britton–Robinson buffer solution at pH 4, observing a peak at a potential close to +1.13 V (vs Ag/AgCl). The developed electrochemical sensor allowed the quantification of thymol over the range of 0.6 to 15 ppm [19].

Kowalcze and Jakubowska reported a multivariate partial least-squares calibration model for the simultaneous detection of eugenol, carvacrol, and thymol in acetate solution at pH 6 using boron-doped diamond electrode and the differential pulse voltammetry. The chemometric-assisted analysis was based on the evaluation of the peak of eugenol at a potential of 715 mV (vs Ag/AgCl) and carvacrol and thymol at a potential of 940 and 955 mV (vs Ag/AgCl), respectively [20].

The advantages of using carbon-based nanomaterials have been well demonstrated in the literature regarding improved sensitivity and low applied potential required. In this regard, Feng et al. [21]. used a nanocomposite constituted of poly(diallyldimethylammonium chloride), graphene-MoS₂ nanoflower, and gold nanoparticles to modify the glassy carbon electrode for the quantification of eugenol in amperometric mode at an applied potential of 0.582 V (vs Ag/AgCl). This electrochemical sensor detected eugenol in acetate buffer solution (pH=5.5) with a linear range of 0.016 and 72 ppm. At the same strength, Fadillah et al. [22]. developed a carbon paste electrode modified with a

nanocomposite constituted of graphene oxide and tin oxide nanoparticles to detect eugenol. By using differential pulse voltammetry, the target analyte was quantified in phosphate buffer solution with a linear range of 0.008–72 ppm, evaluating the peak intensity at a potential of ca. 650 mV. The advantages of using carbon nanotubes were reported by the Escarpa group [23], which used single-walled carbon nanotubes screen-printed electrodes to detect thymol and carvacrol with a peak potential close to 500 mV in Sorensen buffer at pH 5, obtaining a linear range up to 14 ppm with a detection limit of 0.6 ppm. The functionality of carbon nanotubes has been further exploited by Yang et al. [24]., which combined the electrocatalytic activity of carbon nanotubes with the selectivity and sensitivity of molecularly imprinted polymers. To do this, the authors used molecularly imprinted poly (*p*-aminobenzenethiol-co-*p*-aminobenzoic acid) film and ionic liquid 1-aminopropyl-3-methylimidazolium bromide functionalized with nanocomposite constituted of graphene and carbon nanotubes for the detection of eugenol in the concentration range of 0.08 to 3.3 ppm and the limit of detection equal to 0.016 ppm.

Carbon black (CB) has been recently rediscovered. It is used to produce electrochemical sensors by taking advantage of its exceptional electrochemical properties, including enhanced electron transport and resistance to fouling. Moreover, CB can be utilized precisely as providers have supplied it without any physical or chemical processing, reducing the time as well as chemicals and energy for pre-treatment before the use. In addition, its affordability (around 1 €/Kg) and ease of achieving a stable and homogeneous dispersion are other benefits for producing low-cost and reproducible CB-based sensors. In 2007, Hočevar and Ogorevc reported the first use of CB as a nanomaterial for analyte detection in a liquid phase [25] by using the CB paste micro-electrodes to detect several analytes, including dopamine, ascorbic acid, Cd²⁺, and Pb²⁺. Successively, Svegl et al. [26]. used CB for its deposition on indium tin oxide/glass to detect ascorbic acid, H₂O₂, and copper ions. In 2010, our group demonstrated the huge electroanalytical improvement of the screen-printed electrodes modified by drop casting with CB dispersion to detect several target analytes, including epinephrine, norepinephrine, benzoquinone, and NADH [27], combining the cost-effectiveness of CB and the mass production of the printed electrochemical sensor to deliver cheap nanomodified analytical tools. After that, many (printed)electrochemical sensors have been developed worldwide to detect different target analytes [28]. Among the electrochemical CB-based sensors for the detection of phenolic compounds [29, 30], the first printed sensor reported in the literature detected catechol, gallic acid, caffeic acid, and tyrosol by using miniaturized polyester-based printed electrode CB-modified by drop casting for the quantification of catechol, gallic acid, caffeic acid, and tyrosol with a detection limit of 0.1 μM, 1 μM, 0.8 μM, and 2 μM, respectively [31].

The paper-based analytical devices have attracted massive attention from the scientific community in the last decade. From the first electrochemical paper-based device reported by the Henry group [32], many electrochemical paper-based devices have been developed for a variety of applications in diverse fields, namely biomedical, agrifood, and environmental ones, thanks to their relevant features including their capability to work as a reservoir for the delivery of smart electrochemical (bio)sensors that contain the reagents, fostering their on-site use without any additional task for the end-users [33,34]. Furthermore, the use of paper supplies white devices, as highlighted with RGBfast method by comparing different electrochemical sensors for phosphate detection, including the paper one [35].

Herein, we report the first paper-based device for EOs detection, with the further advantages of using CB low-cost nanomaterial as a nanomodifier. In addition, the paper was used as a reservoir for the reagents needed for the measurement [36] for delivering an ecodesigned, cost-effective, and easy-to-use analytical tool; thus, the end user needs to add only the sample for the analysis. The present device is well integrated into the sustainability vision, by measuring EO *green* antimicrobial agents using *white* paper-based sensors.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Reagents and equipment

Ethanol, carvacrol, thymol, eugenol, dimethylformamide, sodium acetate, acetic acid, Mueller-Hinton broth (MHB) liquid medium, and Mueller-Hinton Agar (MHA) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). CB was kindly gifted by Cabot Corporation (Ravenna, Italy). Potassium chloride was purchased from Carlo Erba (Italy).

Chikungunya virus (CHIKV) was isolated from a human serum sample by the Defense Institute for Biomedical Sciences (Rome, Italy). The minimum essential medium (MEM) supplemented with Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) was from Euroclone S.p.A (Milan, Italy). Vero E6 cells, penicillin, streptomycin, and *Escherichia coli* ATCC 8739 (*E. coli*) were purchased from Thermo Scientific (Waltham, Massachusetts, USA). *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) ATCC 6538P was from Microbiologics (St. Cloud, Minnesota, USA).

DPV was carried out using a portable potentiostat, EmStat3 Blue or SensiSmart (PalmSens, Netherlands), in connection with a computer or smartphone, respectively, by using the PStouch app for data management.

2.2. Paper-based sensor production and modification

Filter paper sheets were firstly modified with an ad hoc designed wax pattern to delimitate the hydrophilic area in which liquid samples were dropped, preventing them from reaching the electrical contacts through capillary permeation. The wax pattern was printed onto filter paper using a ColorQube 8580 Xerox printer and treated at 100 °C for 1 min to allow the wax to permeate through the paper network homogeneously. Then, conductive inks were used to print a three-electrode system onto wax-modified filter paper sheets, by employing a 245 DEK serigraphic printer. The conductive inks were applied through masks with the desired patterns. The working and counter-electrodes were obtained using a graphite-based ink and the pseudo-reference electrode was printed using Ag/AgCl-based ink. The electrode surface was modified with 6 µL of CB dispersion for the detection of thymol, eugenol, and carvacrol.

2.3. Preparation of EO solutions

Thymol was first dissolved in ethanol and the dilutions were prepared in acetate solution 10 mM + potassium chloride 0.1 M (pH 5.0). Eugenol and carvacrol were prepared directly in an acetate solution 10 mM + potassium chloride 0.1 M (pH 5.0).

2.4. Viruses and bacteria preparation

CHIKV, isolated from a human serum sample, was passed once in Vero cells to generate a virus master stock used then to produce the working stocks. Then, the virus was propagated in Vero E6 cells, cultured in MEM supplemented with 2 % FBS and 0.2 U/mL penicillin and 0.2 mg/mL streptomycin. At the onset of 90–100 % cytopathic effect after the infection, the virus was collected by centrifuging the culture supernatants of infected Vero cells at 600 g for 5 min. The clarified supernatant was collected, frozen, and kept at – 80 °C until use. The viral stock titer was determined by plaque assay. The experiments were conducted using a viral titer of 10⁴ PFU/mL.

The bacterial suspensions of *E. coli* ATCC 8739 and *S. aureus* ATCC 6538P were prepared from bacterial strains stored at – 80 °C in cryovials containing porous beads for microbiological culture preservation. These strains were then cultivated overnight in MHB liquid medium. To achieve the appropriate dilution of bacteria, 0.5 McFarland reference suspension was prepared and subsequently verified by measuring the absorbance at a wavelength of 625 nm using a spectrophotometer. The bacterial suspension turbidity was compared to the 0.5 McFarland

suspension, and the bacterial concentration was adjusted through serial dilution to obtain a concentration of 0.5 × 10⁶ CFU/mL, which was also confirmed by seeding serial dilution of the preparation on MHA. The inoculum was utilized for testing within 10 min of preparation to maintain the appropriate cell density (CFU/mL).

2.5. Measurements of EOs in standard solution

DPV was selected for EOs detection by connecting the paper-based sensor to a portable potentiostat connected to a smartphone for the easy management of the data. Before the measurement, the sensor is loaded with 5 µL of acetate solution 10 mM + KCl 0.1 M at pH = 5 and let to dry; then, it is ready for EO detection by adding 5 µL of EO solution at different concentrations. The calibration curves were carried out by analyzing different solutions of thymol, eugenol, and carvacrol in the concentration range comprised between 2 and 16 ppm, using the following electrochemical conditions: Estep = 0.005 V, Scan rate = 0.005 V/s, and Epulse = 0.05 V [20].

2.6. GC-MS method

GC-MS analyses were performed with a SHIMADZU GCMS-QP2010 SE using a SLB-5 ms fused silica capillary column (length= 30 m, thickness= 0.25 µm, diameter= 0.25 µm), with helium as the mobile phase. Data analysis was conducted using LabSolutions-GCMS solutions 2.61 software. The following run parameters were used: Tinj= 250 °C, Splitless injection, Ti= 40 °C (Hold = 2 min), T gradient= 10 °C min⁻¹, Tf= 220 °C (Hold= 2 min), Run time= 20 min.

2.7. Calibration curve in standard solution using GC-MS method

Naphthalene was chosen as an external standard. A 1.00 × 10⁻² M solution was prepared dissolving 1.28 × 10⁻² g of naphthalene into 10.00 mL ethyl acetate. 100.00 mL of 1.00 × 10⁻⁴ M naphthalene solution was prepared by 1:100 dilution of the previous one. Such a solution was freshly prepared before the preparation of the calibration standards of the selected compounds. A 9.92 × 10⁻³ M standard solution was prepared by dissolving 1.49 × 10⁻² g of thymol in 10.00 mL of 1.00 × 10⁻⁴ M naphthalene in ethyl acetate. By serial dilution, 10.00 mL of each of the following standard solutions were prepared in the external standard solution: 9.92 × 10⁻⁴ M (149 ppm), 1.98 × 10⁻⁴ M (29.7 ppm), 1.58 × 10⁻⁴ M (23.8 ppm), 1.28 × 10⁻⁴ M (19.2 ppm), 1.03 × 10⁻⁴ M (15.4 ppm), 8.19 × 10⁻⁵ M (12.3 ppm), 6.55 × 10⁻⁵ M (9.84 ppm), 5.90 × 10⁻⁵ M (8.86 ppm). A 9.98 × 10⁻² M standard solution was prepared by dissolving 1.50 × 10⁻² g of carvacrol in 10.00 mL 1.00 × 10⁻⁴ M naphthalene in ethyl acetate. By serial dilution, 10.00 mL of each of the following standard solutions were prepared in the external standard solution: 9.98 × 10⁻³ M (150 ppm), 4.99 × 10⁻⁴ M (75.0 ppm), 1.66 × 10⁻⁴ M (24.9 ppm), 9.96 × 10⁻⁵ M (15.0 ppm), 7.97 × 10⁻⁵ M (12.0 ppm), 5.58 × 10⁻⁵ M (8.37 ppm). A 1.71 × 10⁻² M standard solution was prepared dissolving 2.80 × 10⁻² g of eugenol in 10.00 mL 1.00 × 10⁻⁴ M naphthalene in ethyl acetate. By serial dilution, 10.00 mL of each of the following standard solutions were prepared in the external standard solution: 1.71 × 10⁻³ M (281 ppm), 1.71 × 10⁻⁴ M (28.1 ppm), 8.56 × 10⁻⁵ M (14.1 ppm), 6.85 × 10⁻⁵ M (11.2 ppm), 5.14 × 10⁻⁵ M (8.44 ppm). Every standard solution was freshly prepared and measured three times. The calibration curves of thymol, eugenol, and carvacrol are shown in Fig. S1.

2.8. Extraction method

Standard solutions of thymol, carvacrol, and eugenol were prepared in an acetate solution 10 mM + KCl 0.1 M (pH=5), obtaining standard solutions at 10 ppm, 12 ppm, and 16 ppm concentrations. The extraction of such organic compounds from the aqueous solutions was performed three times, individually, for each selected concentration of the standard

solution of each compound, through the following extraction procedure: 1) 1.00 mL of aqueous standard solution is extracted with a total of 4.00 mL dichloromethane (DCM) in 4 portions, dried on anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and filtered on basic alumina, carefully washing the vial with DCM. 2) DCM is removed under a constant flow of nitrogen gas. 3) The residue is dissolved in 1.00 mL of 1.00×10^{-4} M naphthalene solution in ethyl acetate. The resulting sample is then subjected to GC-MS analysis.

2.9. Tool used for greenness and whiteness evaluation

The RGBfast developed by Nowak et al. [35], was used to assess the greenness and whiteness of the device.

3. Results and discussion

With the overriding goal of developing a paper-based electrochemical sensor for the detection of the selected EOs, we first optimized the modification of the working electrode surface with CB and the parameters of the electrochemical technique used, namely differential pulse voltammetry (DPV).

To deliver a reagent-free device, the paper-based sensor was loaded before the measurement with 5 μL of the acetate buffer and waited for the volatilization of the solvent, to entrap the buffer salt in the cellulose network. In this way, the pre-loaded sensor is ready for the measurement without adjusting of pH. Once the paper-based analytical tool was optimized, we evaluated its analytical performances for detecting the selected EOs in an added 5 μL of solution on the sensor (Fig. 1).

3.1. CB-based electrode for the detection of EOs

The use of CB as a nanomodifier for electrodes is driven by its relevant electrochemical properties in terms of the decrease of applied potential for amperometric detection, the reduction of peak-to-peak separation for reversible species using cyclic voltammetry technique, the improvement of the peak intensity in the all electrochemical analysis, and the decrease of the resistance of the electron transfer due to high surface area. The morphological and structural features of CB N220 were previously characterized by Mazzaracchio et al. [37], using transmission electron microscopy (TEM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and Raman spectroscopy. TEM analysis revealed that CB N220 consists of onion-like carbon structures with particle sizes ranging from 20 to 40 nm. SEM analysis confirmed that CB N220 forms a continuous and uniform layer on the surface of the working electrode, revealing a rough and sponge-like structure characterized by the presence of

numerous and diffuse cauliflower aggregates of CB [38]. Additionally, Raman spectroscopy provided insight into the functional groups and defects of CB N220. The ID/IG ratio of 1.28 indicated a high density of defect sites, crucial for catalytic activity. The already characterized nanomaterial is used for the first time for EO detection. In detail, in the presence of CB onto the working electrode surface, the sensor gives a higher-intensity oxidation peak of thymol, eugenol, and carvacrol with respect to the bare electrode, as shown in Fig. 2. Indeed, the presence of CB increased the sensitivity, owing to the high surface area and enhanced conductivity [28]. The sensor-response is similar to the one obtained in the case of tyrosine, which is the phenolic compound characterized by the presence of only one OH group [39]. On the contrary, the electrochemical response differs from the one obtained in the case of catechol, caffeic acid, gallic acid, and tyrosol, phenolic compounds characterized by the presence of OH groups, in which we have observed both enhanced intensity peak current and decreased peak potential [31]. This behaviour can probably be ascribed to the improved carbocation stability in the presence of OH groups, which easily react with the alkene group of CB, allowing for a further decrease of the redox potential.

3.2. Effect of CB amount on the working electrode surface

The determination of the volume of CB to be cast onto the surface of the electrode is a crucial step in achieving efficient detection of EOs. The impact of the quantity of CB was investigated by depositing a dispersion of CB with a concentration of 1 mg/mL in the range of 2 to 8 μL , followed by the measurement of 8 ppm of thymol. As shown in Fig. 3A, a volume of 6 μL of CB demonstrated the best compromise between sensitivity and reproducibility, using the paper-based device. This volume of CB was chosen to be cast onto the surface of the working electrode for further investigations.

3.3. Optimization of the experimental parameters

After the optimization of the volume of the CB solution, the parameters of the DPV technique were investigated. The influence of the potential step (Estep) was assessed in the range comprised between 1 and 15 mV, as shown in Fig. 3B. Among the tested values, 5 mV demonstrated the most favorable performance in terms of peak current intensity and reproducibility (RSD % equal to 6 %). Hence, this specific value was chosen to detect the selected EOs. The effect of the scan rate was evaluated by varying this parameter in the range of 2.5 - 20 mV/s. As shown in Fig. 3C, the best result in terms of recorded current intensity

Fig. 1. CB-paper-based sensor for EO detection.

Fig. 2. A) Differential pulse voltammograms by measuring thymol 8 ppm, using bare electrode and electrode modified with 6 μL of CB. B) Differential pulse voltammograms by measuring eugenol 8 ppm, using bare electrode and electrode modified with 6 μL of CB. C) Differential pulse voltammograms by measuring carvacrol 8 ppm, using bare electrode and electrode modified with 6 μL of CB.

was obtained with a value of 2.5 mV/s; however, with a scan rate of 5 mV/s a better reproducibility was obtained, as well as a higher resolution of the signal peak (data not shown), thus it was selected as scan rate value. The influence of the Epulse was subsequently investigated within the range of 25 and 150 mV. The best compromise between the intensity of the current and the reproducibility was achieved at 50 mV, as shown in Fig. 3D. Consequently, this Epulse was chosen due to the aforementioned reasons. Finally, to satisfy the user-friendly requirement, the reagent-free approach was evaluated. In detail, the paper-based sensor response was tested without and with the reagent-free approach. In the first case (no reagent-free approach) 70 μL of acetate solution 10 mM + KCl 0.1 M (pH 5) containing 12 ppm of thymol was added to the paper-based electrode. In the second case (reagent-free approach), the testing area was previously pre-loaded with 5 μL of a 10 mM acetate buffer solution (pH 5) + KCl 0.1 M. The measurement of thymol solution 12 ppm was easily carried out by adding 5 μL of sample prepared in distilled water onto the testing area. As shown in Fig. 3E-F, the voltammograms obtained do not show significant differences, demonstrating the reliability of the reagent-free approach, which renders the device easy to use; only the addition of 5 μL of the sample is required without any dilution step or reagent addition.

3.4. EO detection in standard solutions

Under these optimized conditions, the electrochemical performance of the CB-paper-based sensor for detecting EOs was evaluated by measuring the standard solution of thymol, eugenol, and carvacrol in the concentration range comprised between 2 and 16 ppm. As reported in Fig. 4, the current responses were proportional to EO concentrations, obtaining linearity described by the following equations $y = (0.12 \pm 0.01)x - (0.004 \pm 0.065)$, $R^2 = 0.985$ (thymol), $y = (0.078 \pm 0.004)x + (0.08 \pm 0.04)$, $R^2 = 0.979$ (eugenol), and $y = (0.051 \pm 0.003)x + (0.04 \pm 0.03)$, $R^2 = 0.964$ (carvacrol). The detection limit was 0.1, 0.1, and 0.2 ppm, calculated as ratio signal/noise (S/N) equal to 3. Furthermore, the precision of the proposed method was estimated by the RSD % measuring 8 ppm of EOs using three different sensors, obtaining an RSD % equal to 3 %, 2 %, and 5 % for thymol, eugenol, and carvacrol, respectively.

3.5. Interference study

The selectivity of the CB-paper-based sensor was evaluated by investigating the effects of other used electroactive antibacterial agents, namely Ag^+ and Cu^{2+} [40,41]. No peak was observed in both cases, demonstrating the absence of interference in the case of these selected antimicrobial agents (Fig. 5A). Because the antimicrobial activity is based on the interaction between the EOs and bacteria/viruses, we evaluated the response of carvacrol 8 ppm in the presence of CHIKV ($1 \times$

10^4 PFU/mL), *E. coli* (0.5×10^6 CFU/mL), and *S. aureus* (0.5×10^6 CFU/mL). These concentrations were selected to demonstrate that the presence of a high amount of bacteria and viruses does not interfere with the measurement of EOs, taking carvacrol as the model compound. As depicted in Fig. 5B, the signal recorded in the presence of these interferents showed no significant variations, demonstrating the selectivity of the developed sensor.

3.6. Recovery study

To evaluate the trueness of the method, firstly, we added EOs at the concentration of 16 ppm in a matrix like seawater, considering the use of EOs in the aquaculture sector, and no electroanalytical response was observed for all EOs tested (Fig. 6). These results are probably due to the fast reaction between the EOs and the matrix components with the change of EOs structure and electrochemical properties, hindering the known electrochemical reaction at the working electrode surface of the EOs. To verify this hypothesis, the spiked solutions were also analyzed with GC-MS and no peaks related to EOs were observed. To further demonstrate that the sensor is capable of detecting EOs when they are active, we added a high concentration of EOs, for having unreacted EOs in the sample. For instance, we observed a peak corresponding to a concentration higher than 16 ppm when e.g. thymol 1000 ppm was added (data not shown), demonstrating that EOs are detected when they did not react with the compounds present in the matrix. To further assess the reliability of this device, the accuracy was evaluated by recovery study and by comparison with GC-MS used as a laboratory set-up method [42–44]. Firstly, recovery studies were carried out at three levels in standard solutions, namely 10, 12, and 16 ppm, for thymol, eugenol, and carvacrol, obtaining good recovery values reported in Table S1. After, the same studies were performed by GC-MS analyses, achieving comparable results between the sensor and GC-MS, demonstrating the good accuracy of this device. In this way, we demonstrated that this paper-based electrochemical sensor is capable of detecting EOs with sensitivity and accuracy by using a miniaturized, cost-effective, and easy-to-use device. To evaluate the accuracy of the method, the Bias % was calculated for each recovery level (10, 12, and 16 ppm) for thymol, eugenol, and carvacrol, comparing the measured concentrations to the nominal values. The results are reported in Table S2, showing frequent Bias % values within the acceptable range of ± 5 % for all analytes, further confirming the accuracy of the method. These results go beyond the state of the art compared to the electrochemical sensors for the detection of EOs published up to now (Table S3), considering that CB-paper-based sensor for the detection of thymol, eugenol, and carvacrol, offers several advantages over previously published methods. Compared to some sensors, the CB-paper-based sensor exhibits a significantly lower peak potential (+0.55 V for thymol and carvacrol, +0.45 V for eugenol vs Ag/AgCl), which is advantageous for minimizing

Fig. 3. A) Study of the effect of CB-dispersion volume (μL) cast on the working electrode surface. Histogram obtained by measuring $70\ \mu\text{L}$ of acetate solution $10\ \text{mM}$ + KCl $0.1\ \text{M}$ (pH 5) containing thymol $8\ \text{ppm}$, using electrodes modified with 2, 4, 6, and $8\ \mu\text{L}$ of CB. B) Study of the effect of Estep. Histogram obtained by measuring $70\ \mu\text{L}$ of acetate solution $10\ \text{mM}$ + KCl $0.1\ \text{M}$ (pH 5) containing thymol $8\ \text{ppm}$. Estep values: 1, 2.5, 5, 10, and $15\ \text{mV}$. C) Study of the effect of the scan rate. Histogram obtained by measuring $70\ \mu\text{L}$ of acetate solution $10\ \text{mM}$ + KCl $0.1\ \text{M}$ (pH 5) containing thymol $8\ \text{ppm}$. Scan rate values: 2.5, 5, 10, and $20\ \text{mV/s}$. D) Study of the effect of the Epulse. Histogram obtained by measuring $70\ \mu\text{L}$ of acetate solution $10\ \text{mM}$ + KCl $0.1\ \text{M}$ (pH 5) containing thymol $8\ \text{ppm}$. Epulse values: 25, 50, 100, and $150\ \text{mV}$. E) Differential pulse voltammogram obtained by measuring $70\ \mu\text{L}$ of acetate solution $10\ \text{mM}$ + KCl $0.1\ \text{M}$ (pH 5) containing $12\ \text{ppm}$ of thymol. F) Differential pulse voltammogram obtained by using reagent-free approach and measuring $5\ \mu\text{L}$ of thymol $12\ \text{ppm}$ prepared in distilled water.

Fig. 4. A) Differential pulse voltammograms and calibration curves obtained by measuring 5 μL of sample containing different concentrations of thymol: 2, 4, 8, 12, and 16 ppm. B) Differential pulse voltammograms and calibration curves obtained by measuring 5 μL of sample containing different concentrations of eugenol: 2, 4, 8, 12, and 16 ppm. C) Differential pulse voltammograms and calibration curves obtained by measuring 5 μL of sample containing different concentrations of carvacrol: 2, 4, 8, 12, and 16 ppm.

Fig. 5. A) Histogram and differential pulse voltammograms obtained by measuring different solutions containing carvacrol 8 ppm, Ag^+ 8 ppm, Cu^{2+} 8 ppm, *CHIKV* 1×10^4 PFU/mL, *E. coli* 0.5×10^6 CFU/mL, and *S. aureus* 0.5×10^6 CFU/mL. B) Differential pulse voltammograms obtained by measuring the solution containing carvacrol 8 ppm + *E. coli* 0.5×10^6 CFU/mL, and the solution containing carvacrol 8 ppm + *S. aureus* 0.5×10^6 CFU/mL.

interference and energy consumption. This performance is superior to other sensors, such as the glassy carbon electrodes (GCE) with peak potentials of +1.36 V for thymol and +1.33 V for carvacrol [18], the boron-doped diamond electrodes (BDEs) with a peak potential of +1.13 V for thymol [19], and the BDDE sensor with peak potentials of +0.96 V for thymol, +0.94 V for carvacrol, and +0.72 V for eugenol [20]. Notably, a key innovation lies in using a paper-based device, making the sensor reagent-free, portable, and cost-effective while ensuring environmental sustainability. Unlike conventional electrodes such as GCEs or BDEs, which require more complex fabrication processes, the CB-paper-based is simpler to produce and more suitable for large-scale manufacturing. Furthermore, incorporating CB enhances the sensitivity and selectivity due to its high surface area and defect sites, enabling efficient electron transfer.

3.7. Greenness and whiteness evaluation of EOs detection using paper-based sensor vs GC-MS using RGBfast

The concept of White Analytical Chemistry extends beyond traditional green metrics, incorporating a comprehensive evaluation of analytical methods by considering greenness, analytical performances, and practical benefits. To assess the degree of greenness and whiteness of the developed paper-based sensor compared to the reference method GC-MS, the RGBfast model was applied. This model is an enhanced and automated evolution of the original RGB framework capable of simplifying and accelerating the assessment process by focusing on six critical variables that effectively combine multiple aspects of analytical methods. Unlike previous models, RGBfast integrates features like the ChlorTox Scale, offering a transparent, user-friendly, and computationally efficient evaluation tool. The RGBfast model provides a structured and automated tool for evaluating analytical methods based on three core parameters: Red (analytical performances), Green

Fig. 6. A) Differential pulse voltammograms were obtained by measuring 5 μL of seawater containing thymol 16 ppm. B) Differential pulse voltammograms were obtained by measuring 5 μL of seawater containing eugenol 16 ppm. C) Differential pulse voltammograms were obtained by measuring 5 μL of seawater containing carvacrol 16 ppm. D) GC–MS analysis performed by measuring sea water containing thymol 16 ppm. E) GC–MS analysis performed by measuring seawater containing eugenol 16 ppm. F) GC–MS analysis performed by measuring sea water containing carvacrol 16 ppm.

(environmental sustainability), and Blue (practicality and productivity).

In this study, the whiteness evaluation was conducted using RGBfast software, which quantifies scores proportionally across the three parameters.

The results of this comparison are summarized in Fig. 7, which illustrates the performances for both methods. The RGBfast evaluation reveals that the paper-based sensor demonstrates a significantly higher whiteness score, as indicated by the clear distinction in RGB metrics, compared to the lower score observed for GC–MS. This improved performance underscores the sensor's enhanced sustainability, positioning it as a benchmark for environmentally conscious approaches in EO detection.

4. Conclusions

This study presents the first paper-based electrochemical sensor for

the detection of essential oils, specifically thymol, eugenol, and carvacrol, leveraging carbon black as an effective and cost-efficient nano-material for electrode modification. The proposed sensor stands out for its reagent-free design, achieved by pre-loading the sensor with acetate buffer salts. Thus, without any other task, the end-user detects the essential oils only by adding 5 μL onto the sensor. This innovative approach simplifies the analysis process for the end user while minimizing environmental impact, aligning with the principles of sustainability. A comparative evaluation using the RGBfast model highlighted the device's superior whiteness compared to conventional chromatographic techniques like GC–MS. The sensor exhibited significant advantages in terms of reduced reagent consumption, lower energy use, and minimal waste generation. Additionally, its portability, ease of use, and affordability make it an ideal tool for onsite applications in environmental monitoring. Thus, this device offers a sustainable and practical solution for the rapid and accurate detection of natural

GC-MS			Paper-based electrochemical sensor		
Individual criteria			Individual criteria		
R1: Accuracy	R2: Precision	R3: LOD	R1: Accuracy	R2: Precision	R3: LOD
49,3	52,6	35,3	50,8	47,6	85,5
G1: ChlorTox		G2/B2: Energy	G1: ChlorTox		G2/B2: Energy
33,4		37,2	99,1		76,2
B1: Sample throughput			B1: Sample throughput		
13,9			64,8		
Color saturation			Color saturation		
Red:	45,1	White:	Red:	59,1	White:
Green:	34,6	31	Green:	90,8	72
Blue:	19,3		Blue:	68,4	
Conclusion			Conclusion		
GC-MS seems not most green			Paper-based electrochemical sensor seems most green		
GC-MS seems not most white			Paper-based electrochemical sensor seems most white		

Fig. 7. Results obtained using RGBfast method for the GC-MS method and the paper-based electrochemical sensor.

antimicrobial compounds, enlarging the use of paper-based devices for essential oils.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Luca Fiore: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Arianna Antinucci:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Giorgia Leotta:** Formal analysis, Data curation. **Laura Fabiani:** Data curation. **Alessandro Iannini:** Validation, Data curation. **Pierluca Galloni:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Riccardo De Santis:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Andrea Ciammaruconi:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Giorgia Grilli:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Elisa Recchia:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Florigio Lista:** Writing – original draft. **Fabiana Arduini:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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